

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 1, April - 2022 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 27649733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12548044

EXTRAJUDICIAL INVENTORIES IN CALDAS NOVAS: ANALYSIS OF SPEED AND LEGAL CERTAINTY

AUTHORS

Rosangela Aurélia da Silva: Graduating in Law at the Faculty of Caldas Novas. Pedagogue from the Faculty of Caldas Novas (2014). Scribe at the Hugo Rocha registry office in Caldas Novas

Rogério do Nascimento Carvalho: University professor and coordinator of the Law course at the Faculty of Caldas Novas. Master's degree in Maritime Strategy from the Naval War College. PhD student at PROLAM-USP. Lawyer

ABSTRACT

This article aims to present the impact of the service already available for extrajudicial inventories and the importance of the future operator who, when studying law, must be prepared to meet this demand. The analysis and with numbers collected at the Hugo Rocha Registry Office, in the city of Caldas Novas-GO, aims to open up a field of action for future professionals who need to adapt to new skills. The objective of the work aims to understand the phenomenon of dejuridification and what meaning it impacts the legal world. The field research brings an external vector that shows how notary offices and legal operators have prepared themselves to respond to demands that tend to grow due to agility and legal security. The scenario in which these changes occur is the living environment of law, which is constantly changing. The transition from judicial acts to extrajudicial acts is accompanied by legal certainty, which leads to a growing demand for agility in relation to the service of the Judiciary. It is a portrait of the future that is increasingly present and needs the preparation of the academic, which will soon be a reality.

Keywords: Extrajudicial inventory. Dejuridification. Operator of the law.

INTRODUCTION

The case study that deals with the preparation of inventories that involve adults and capable people and, still, without divergence in the division of assets, has undergone modifications of competences whose redirection to the extrajudicial scope has gained shape in recent years, aiming to give greater speed and effectiveness in acts that redistribute the ownership of assets.

The work seeks to present the circumstances in which the displacement of competences from the judicial to the extrajudicial forum is the translation of the moment to which it reserves emphasis on notarial and notarial services that increasingly need legal operators for the preparation of such services, which in itself shows the importance of the study of the subject and its legal consequences.

However, the problem situation is demonstrated in the effectiveness or not of the provision of services and how to ensure the legal certainty of the extrajudicial act without the direct analysis of the judge in these cases. Therefore, as a general objective, it seeks to analyze the displacement of competence and its motivation without losing the authenticity of the act and making it valid before third parties and society.

Regarding the specific objectives, this article illustrates the competence of the notary offices of the district of Caldas Novas, its specificities and differences, with emphasis on the allocation of inventories in the Hugo Rocha notary's office, the object of this study. In addition, the speed of the deadline and, finally, the legal certainty of the act also permeates, in compliance with the rules of the internal affairs department of the Court of Justice of Goiás (TJGO).

It is clear, therefore, with the annual numerical evolution of the service provided and which changes bring greater speed to this procedure. Therefore, the hypothesis to be answered in the investigation aims to answer the following question: Is there confidence in the displacement of competence from judicial to extrajudicial acts in inventories that are processed with adults and capables.

The topic addressed draws the attention of the legal and academic community, as it will bring

more professionals to military in the area, which displaces the traditional forum. The motivation of the academic in the subject lies in the fact that she works in the environment object of study and is in the law course to carry out a public examination of titles and documents to assume the function of an extrajudicial notary.

To this end, the present analysis focuses on specialized doctrines, tabulation of internal numbers carried out by open and public research to the data of the registry and, with the field research in which it seeks to trace such differences, solidifying the present position and, consequently, the evolution of the application of the law in the district.

In addition, the case focuses on contributing to the sociological understanding of the phenomenon of dejuridification, as well as the implications in the procedural legal sphere and in the division of assets that can be carried out quickly and effectively.

DEVELOPMENT

The Hugo Rocha Notary Office and its material and territorial competence

The Hugo Rocha Notary's Office, official designation of the Second Notary Public and the Registry of Titles and Documents and Legal Entities of the Municipality of Caldas Novas-GO, has as its current holder Hugo Andreany Rocha who, since 2014, assumed the function as approved in a public tender of titles and documents and designated to fully exercise, such a function.

The notary public originates through the creation that took place on 05/20/1930. The competencies of the Second Notary Public of Caldas Novas can be divided into exclusive and common. The former are reserved for the services of Protest, Registry of Deeds and Documents and Legal Entities, while the others are intended for Notary Public. For the present study, we will focus on the competence of the Notary Public in making extrajudicial inventories and their impact on the composition of the other services provided by this service.

Currently, with 22 employees, three are assigned to exclusively attend to the extrajudicial inventory

procedure. The basic training of the operators who are allocated to the function has training in: law, pedagogy and high school. In total, most of the other attendants have a college degree, as shown in Chart 1:

Table 1 – Number of officials with tertiary and secondary education

Source: Prepared by the authors (2024)

Table 2 – Courses for officials with higher education

Source: Prepared by the authors (2024)

As there may be mobility among the other sectors of the Notary, it is important to emphasize the correlation between law graduates as preponderant in the daily treatment of the functions of service to the population, which indicates a trend of dominance in the service of the notary for this purpose.

Among the employees who are directly allocated to carry out the extrajudicial inventory services, there are three of them, one of whom has a bachelor's degree in law, another has a degree in pedagogy currently studying law and another with high school and is studying law. Therefore, it is a common trait to study law for these skills.

This proves, however, the relevance and correlates the allocation of forensic services to the competence of the notary public to citizens with expertise in the legal and social sciences. Such predominance is configured by legal certainty.

With the prospect of being allocated greater competences, to serve by the phenomenon of dejudicialization, it is a public and notorious fact that the number of collaborators must be increased and, for the most part, by law graduates, even by the current projection.

Therefore, there are opportunities for future holders of higher education, whose remuneration is around R\$ 2,500.00 (two thousand five hundred reais), higher than the average of the city of Caldas Novas, whose tourist position pays less than in the extrajudicial notary's office. Through experience, it can aim for securitization through public tender, which has been one of the best in the country.

The role of the notary office studied is to meet the needs of the population and, at the same time, to streamline public services to bring better efficiency and legal certainty. The ongoing process demonstrates confidence and robustness, whose capacity is essential to generate experiences for future generations and, thus, expand the scope of the list of possibilities of the future operator of the law.

Thus, it is denoted that the dejudicialization and the increase of competences to notaries should be seen by law operators as a possible path towards the professional success of the citizens of Caldas Novas.

The out-of-court development of inventories in the Brazilian legal scenario

The main concepts and definitions on the subject of extrajudicial development are embedded within the process of de-juridification that has gradually been systematizing the national legislation. This is an ongoing process in the national legal panorama and, therefore, instrumentalized by measures that, in principle, can lead to agility to official procedures, promoted in notary offices and supervised by the internal affairs departments of the state Courts of Justice and federal rules.

Law No. 11,441/2007 innovates the legal system

by authorizing, among other items, the possibility of making an inventory by extrajudicial means through the country's notary offices and notaries. On the other hand, Resolution No. 35/2007 of the National Council of Justice (CNJ) focuses on clarifying the procedure by providing legal certainty and ruling out the possibility of fraud and misappropriation of assets.

The deeds of judicial inventory are titles capable of being used in the civil registry and real estate registry, for the transfer of assets and rights, as well as for the promotion of all acts necessary for the materialization of transfers of assets and the collection of values (article 3 of Resolution 35 of the CNJ). In this context, with the public deed, it is possible to transfer the deceased's real estate, as well as nominal shares, amounts deposited in bank accounts and vehicles owned by the deceased (TARTUCE, 2020, p. 587).

Tartuce (2022) indicates that the out-of-court inventory must be prepared by means of a public deed, which rules out judicial review. However, it initially asserts that this route can only be used when there is an agreement between the parties, full civil capacity and the absence of a will "I note that notaries are already practicing inventory and partition deeds with full effects, regardless of judicial approval, and without further questioning in this regard" (TARTUCE, 2022, p. 1667).

The public deed, as the name itself mentions, is a solemn act with formalities that enshrine pillars of the legal transaction. With due respect, it is able to establish foundations that support the necessary legal order when there is no valid and current will to be observed.

Gagliano and Pamplona Filho (2020) warn that the extrajudicial inventory needs to meet the legal requirements as a means of carrying out a right, because, according to the authors, if there is no conflict of interest, there must be devices capable of asserting the title with legal certainty capable of registering the will of the parties who, in turn, It implies the annotation of the registration of real estate and the transfer of assets.

On this point, the national jurisprudence establishes

the parameters in several judgments in which it indicates that the extrajudicial inventory, as long as the requirements of legality and procedure are met, can be an option of the party, which is not an obstacle to the realization of the judicial version.

Tartuce (2020) also lists that the development of this procedure in the national legal routine must be mandatory the presence of the law operator with regular registration with the Brazilian Bar Association (OAB), as well as it is possible to obtain the gratuity of the extrajudicial act, because "to obtain such a benefit, the simple declaration of the interested parties that they are unable to afford the fees is enough, even if the parties are assisted by a lawyer" (TARTUCE, 2020, p. 588).

However, the author asserts that some provisions are not yet settled in the various units of the federation, such as the exemption or not of power of attorney in the drafting of the public deed, which still requires jurisprudential understanding for the standardization of procedures throughout the country.

As for essential requirements, Tartuce (2020) recalls that the appointment of an inventor is a requirement for validity, since he represents the estate, as well as the public deed can be rectified with the consent of the parties. Hence, the importance of full civil capacity or emancipation, to give speed and regularity to the extrajudicial procedure.

In addition, there is the need to pay taxes due (if any) and also the possibility of assigning hereditary rights, if it is of peaceful consensus of the heirs. However, there is no consensus between the public treasury and the doctrine in the case where there are hyposufficient heirs, in which Tartuce (2022) cites the concern of applying the rule when it is impossible to comply with it. "if there are hyposufficient heirs, unable to pay taxes, the rule should be set aside" (TARTUCE, 2022, p. 1672).

Finally, Tartuce (2020) and Gagliano and Pamplona Filho (2020) draw attention to the fact that the procedural act is covered by the qualification of the heirs and the respective presentation of original documents or duly authenticated reprographs to attest to the veracity and, thus, be able to carry out the transmission safely and guaranteed of the act to third parties in good faith.

The greatest innovation of the extrajudicial procedure, according to Tartuce (2020), is the possibility of applying the act to deaths prior to Law 11,441 of 2007 and the prohibition of assets or rights located abroad. Even so, the instrument can be carried out at any time by the heirs, as there will be the application of levied taxes and eventually a fine for delay to a percentage defined in state rules, since such a desideratum is of constitutional competence of the federation units.

Finally, the development of this procedure aims to ensure a quick and safe option for the parties and demonstrates the evolution of the extrajudicial rite that, because it does not have the same limitations as the forums and the specialized state justice, can be developed with greater effectiveness and speed. It is, therefore, a hypothesis that must remain in the sphere of succession and that requires capable operators to carry out such procedures.

The effectiveness of the notarial service provided in the execution of extrajudicial inventories

The main line of research on this topic is illustrated in the works of Tartuce (2022) and Gagliano and Pamplona Filho (2020). Both indicate that the effective service is the hallmark of extrajudicial notaries and, therefore, their effectiveness is justified in the present analysis described below.

It is interesting to add the legal provision that institutionalizes the procedure in order to grant legal certainty to the deed.

Art. 610. If there is a will or an incapacitated interested party, a judicial inventory will be carried out.

§ 1 If all are able and agree, the inventory and distribution may be made by public deed, which shall constitute a document capable of any act of registration, as well as for the collection of amounts deposited in financial institutions.

§ 2 The notary public will only draw up the public deed if all interested parties are assisted by a lawyer or public defender, whose qualification and signature will appear in the notarial act (BRASIL, 2015).

Corroborating the above provision, it must be

assumed that the importance of the act arises from the will of the parties and their capacity, as reiterated in article 2.015 of the Civil Code, which reverberates as follows: "If the heirs are capable, they may make an amicable partition, by public deed, term in the inventory records, or private writing, approved by the judge" (BRASIL, 2002).

The legal basis, therefore, when described in legal diplomas, establishes and authorizes the procedure to be carried out extrajudicially. Therefore, a question could remain in the air: Would the extrajudicial notaries be effective in carrying out such procedures safely and meeting the citizen's wishes?

In fact, the meaning of effectiveness is given by the law whose permission aims to expand the scope of the public service, giving it transparency and assertiveness. Extrajudicial and judicial notaries are not subject to the Consumer Protection Code: they are inspected by the Court of Justice of each state, through the Ombudsman's Office, if any, and the Internal Affairs Office. It is also possible to complain to the Anoreg section of each state, which forwards the complaint to the Internal Affairs Department of the Court of Justice (AGÊNCIA SENADO, 2006).

With this, we point out that the procedures have a connection with the Judiciary and, therefore, the unilateral will of the notary or notary is not imposed, but rather the compliance with imposing norms of which it is not possible to make an extensive interpretation, but rather execution within the legal basis of its competence and jurisdiction.

For Tartuce (2020), the judicial procedure should be reserved for complex cases, even to justify the adoption of the procedure, as the advance is equivalent to the previously existing divorce processes and, within these, making the division of assets.

Therefore, the author points out, such deliberation aims to balance procedures and, at the same time, dejudicialize civil claims, producing speed and consequent elimination of bureaucracy with unnecessary comings and goings of forensic

process when it can be easily overcome in the notarial administrative sphere, with “reductions of bureaucracy and formalities for acts of hereditary transmission, as well as speed, in line with the current trend of dejudicialization of disputes and claims” (TARTUCE, 2020, p. 589).

Gagliano and Pamplona Filho (2020) replicate the understanding of the National Council of Justice by stating that the objective of the procedure is to foster amicable sharing, removing bureaucratic obstacles and advocating agility. The presence or absence of a lawyer in the deed was also conveyed in the debates, but the thesis of the importance of the law operator as a way to ensure the application of the law prevailed, although the discussion also permeates its costs, which traditionally make the preparation of the final document more expensive for heirs whose assets are diminished by assuming such a condition.

The main divergences found on the theme of effectiveness are in the works of Tartuce (2020) and Gagliano and Pamplona Filho (2020). A theme little allocated in the second doctrine, it is still possible to mention the reflection of the recent legal provision and, therefore, still needs a greater passage of time for the reflection of the doctrine as a constitutive element of effectiveness. On the other hand, the classical procedural doctrine of Humberto Theodoro Júnior teaches us that,

[...] Among adults and capables who are in full agreement as to how to divide the hereditary estate, nothing recommends or justifies the recourse to the judicial process and the submission to its costs, its complexity and its inevitable delay. On the other hand, the removal of the inventory from the judicial sphere contributes to relieving the justice system of a significant overload of cases. This system, therefore, only deserves applause (THEODORO JÚNIOR, 2018, p. 257).

In the words of the eminent professor, the correlation between effectiveness and its gains is allocated to elements that involve costs and time. It is precisely what bothers heirs the most, as this considerably increases expenses and wear and tear between families, so such a possibility is welcome

in the legal world.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the present work is based on the tripartition between the classical doctrine of Tartuce (2020) and Gagliano and Pamplona Filho (2020). However, the uniqueness of the analysis of the above topic causes data from one of the notary offices in the district of Caldas Novas to be aggregated in order to determine numbers of extrajudicial inventories in view of the period that involves its beginning until the year 2024.

The presence of odd elements makes the methods applied in the analysis correlate with each other, allowing the study to be in-depth in order to offer a broad overview of the problem and alert to the importance of the legal operator in the present issue.

To complement the present work, the presence of field research carried out with professionals from the local notary (notary and employee with expertise in the preparation of inventory procedures) and from the local law firm in order to settle and clarify what are the gains of the extrajudicial inventory when compared to the common judicial procedure.

However, the interviews are presented by means of a questionnaire with the wording of five identical questions, to attest to important information that can clarify and resolve legal certainty and confidence of the citizen who can seek the resolution of his demand with efficiency and promptness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The field research was carried out in the city of Caldas Novas-GO, in the first half of 2024, with the premise of meeting what is narrated in this scientific article. The presentation of the field research is presented in such a way as to correlate the way in which the answer was given and, if there was agreement or disagreement, and to what degree it interferes in the composition of the present reasoning.

The first question concerns the development of inventories in extrajudicial notary offices, starting in 2007, and whether there was a need to deploy officials for this purpose. The answers, in this

regard, were identical from the two representatives of the notary's office, emphasizing the possibility of carrying out specific training because the innovation added to the notary's competencies demand personalized service that was not yet available. For the lawyer, the importance of highlighting serves to encompass clients since the common service between all extrajudicial services paves the way with possibilities that lead to more services and, consequently, increase foreign exchange, which fosters competition, therefore, he highlights that the displacement of employees serves to apply in a more profitable activity because it is directly connected with the patrimony.

The second question is related to the increase in demand for services for the notary's office after the adoption of the extrajudicial inventory service and the response of both interviewees was positive, but with different perspectives. On the internal side of the counter, it needs training and knowledge of the employee who will prepare the service, while for the legal operator, the migration of the forum allows us to affirm that a new frontier of service also needs to have professionals prepared to deal with less bureaucratization and agility.

When asked about the positive and negative points of the notary performing this type of service, the answers showed a complementary and divergent bias. In the complementary aspect, it was necessary to clarify the positive points that made the agility clear and consigned legal certainty as an element of attraction of the impact of the change from the judicial to the extrajudicial field. On the other hand, the divergence lies in the fact that there was no mention of negative aspects by the interviewees in the registry office, although the professional in the area of law warns about the professional training of those who handle the procedure, if they

necessarily have the same conditions as the servant of the judiciary.

The fourth question discusses the growth of extrajudicial demand, whether there is the impact of the need to prepare legal operators for this specific purpose and the response of both was unanimous in corroborating that the law course is an essential point and closer to meeting the demands of the extrajudicial service. The first interviewee points out that the filling of vacancies of employees currently there is already a predominance of academics or bachelors in law, which points to the service as a highlight in the production and elaboration of the procedures of these processes in question here.

The last question concerns the legal certainty with the notarial service and those who supervise it and it is still more agile and secure than in the judicial process. At this point, we also noticed the convergence of the answers when they mentioned the control by institutions linked to the judiciary, which allows the transmission of the service with the advantage of reducing the number of cases and, thus, being able to relieve the number of records, which can grant greater accessibility to the citizen and also agility in the processing of cases in forums and other judicial instances.

The results are presented with the numbers that indicate the importance and impact of the preparation of procedures, described in Chart 3 and which corroborate with the researched doctrine and the field research whose correlation of the innovation of the service awakens the opening of opportunities for the academic community, especially the law course.

Table 3 – Number of inventories at the Hugo Rocha Notary Office from 2007 to 2023

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on public data available in the service (2024).

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Chart 3 shows the exponential growth of the service and the need for employees able to carry out these fees. The trend that emerges with these data is the expansion of the service, given the complexity that some procedures may have, whether to quantify taxable value, tax to be collected and eventual assignment of rights or donation. The increase in this magnitude also indicates a change in the composition of the entry of fees and amounts destined to notaries who, in turn, need to offer conditions of agility and dexterity to citizens, since they have received the grant of the public power to carry out such procedures now extrajudicial.

With the state of the art presented in the field research and in the data collected from the employees internally, it is assumed that there is an influence of the law course as a guiding element of work in the extrajudicial registry office. It is a well-known fact that the probate sector has people responsible for legal notions, which contributes to the attraction of the law course and its displacement becomes a natural process.

It is recommended, therefore, that this theme be explored in the legal and academic environment, since the provision of the service, by allowing competition between notary offices, becomes a relevant factor for greater efficiency and speed and, thus, meeting the demand of the population. On the other hand, it is important to prepare professionals so that they can pass on knowledge to law students, because, in fact, it is a trend that tends to expand.

With regard to the doctrine, the existing proximity makes this change a reality, aiming to compose a scenario of educational elevation and, with this, draws attention to the best qualification in order to meet future demands whose specialties will demand this perspective of proximity to the law to promote the core activity of the notary.

FINAL THOUGHTS

This article explores a relevant and important topic for the field of law, which is called to attention due to the absence of professionals prepared to work in extrajudicial registry offices. It is a relevant fact that the transition of services to this sphere requires

specific training that is not present in law schools. However, according to the numbers presented in the investigation, the demand for professionals is growing and they need the ability to do the work.

Meanwhile, the reality that has been modified must be accompanied by the training of professionals, because according to the numbers shown in the present investigation, the demand for services, in addition to being on the rise, involves at the same time rising monetary values, which in itself corroborates the justification of the academic in choosing this theme for exposition and analysis.

This time, the importance of offering inventories within the extrajudicial orbit implies articulation between academia and civil society, which, in turn, must be sure of the robustness of the service presented, in addition to feasibility, agility and legal certainty, since they are still under the aegis of the internal affairs department of the Courts of Justice of each unit of the corresponding federation.

However, the rereading that implies the adoption of such procedures is a direct result of the process of dejudicialization that is underway in the national and, indeed, international legal scenario. The combination of factors that has increased the demand for cases to the Judiciary in recent decades has left it in a situation of immobility with the resolution of facts prolonged for years, due to the absence of structural support for the knowledge, processing and finalization of them.

On the other hand, in the extrajudicial sphere, there is the observance of the best way to resolve deeds in the sense of granting agility to deeds without promoting accumulation, which would discourage the accomplishment of the service. For this reason, the notary offices do not have the same ties as the structure of the Judiciary, and may have greater freedom to hire and relocate employees, which gives it a comparative advantage in relation to the state agency.

Currently, the growth of the service has been sustained by the vector that leads notarial performance to excellence and, in turn, demands expansion of activities. The ongoing process indicates that more attributions may knock on the door of notaries, which indicates a fact that brings a future of better reception of services, with more

employees and directly impacts the legal sciences, as there will be pressure for the training of qualified professionals with specificity in this area.

It is, therefore, imperative to verify that the general and specific objectives of this article have been met by demonstrating the relationship between the service to be provided and the way to meet the demand of citizens who want to see their expectations satisfied.

Therefore, the evolution of the law is consistent with the expectation of the response of the agile service. Harmonizing conduct is the driving focus of notaries who aim to serve the general population. In this sense, doctrine and field research respond in the sense of making the citizen protagonist in which the instrument of cooperation delimits the resolution of conflicts. As this process is ongoing, it is considered necessary to improve the theme through future debates, which can be revisited by revisiting this article, of which the academic intends to continue at the graduate level.

REFERENCES

AGENCIA SENADO. Fiscalização é responsabilidade dos tribunais de Justiça. Redação. 06 de novembro de 2006. Disponível em: Disponível em: <https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2015-2018/2015/lei/113105.htm>. Acesso em: 21 dez 2023.

BRASIL. Presidência da República. Secretaria-Geral. Subchefia para Assuntos Jurídicos. Lei nº 13.105, de 16 de março de 2015. Código de Processo Civil. Disponível em: <https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2015-2018/2015/lei/113105.htm>. Acesso em: 02 nov 2023.

BRASIL. Presidência da República. Secretaria-Geral. Subchefia para Assuntos Jurídicos. Lei nº 10.406, de 10 de janeiro de 2002. Código Civil. Disponível em: <https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/110406compilada.htm>. Acesso em: 02 nov 2023.

PEIXOTO, Ulisses Vieira Moreira. Manual prático do inventário e da partilha: judicial e extrajudicial - Doutrina e prática. 6.ed. Leme: Editora Mizuno, 2023.

TARTUCE, Flávio. Direito Civil: direito das sucessões, Vol. 6, Rio de Janeiro: Forense, 2018.
THEODORO JÚNIOR, Humberto. Curso de direito processual civil, v. 2, Rio de Janeiro: Forense, 2018.